

Supplementary Table S4. Morphological and ecological trait data included in analyses (see methods for definitions of all traits), with genus/clade, species name, diel activity (1, active during the day or night; 0, active during the day only), turbidity (1, high turbidity; 0, low turbidity), minimum depth, maximum depth, absolute eye diameter, log-transformed eye diameter relative to body whorl width, absolute eye aperture width, lens diameter, log-transformed aperture width relative to lens diameter, absolute rhabdom length, log-transformed rhabdom length relative to lens diameter, body whorl width. Morphological and ecological data are collected from specimens listed in Supplementary Table S2; for sources of turbidity data, see methods. Maximum and minimum depth data were sourced from the literature (see reference list below table), and personal communications with curators [*Canarium darwinense* and *Doxander vittatus* (Richard Willan, NTM, *pers. comm.*); *Doxander vittatus* and *Laevistrombus turturella* B (Siong Kiat Tan, ZRC, *pers. comm.*)]. To support and/or extend these depth ranges, additional depth data were taken from specimens from private collections featured within Wieneke et al. (2022), a web page maintained by leading stromboid taxonomists, and museum collection databases: Natural History Museum, UK; Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle, France; University of Florida, USA; Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History, USA; Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Netherlands; Natuurhistorisch Museum Rotterdam, Netherlands.

Genus / clade	Species	Diel activity	Turbidity	Min. depth (m)	Max. depth (m)	Absolute eye diameter, ED (µm)	log (rel. ED)	Absolute aperture width, AW (µm)	Lens diameter (µm)	log (rel. AW)	Absolute rhabdom length, RL (µm)	log (rel. RL)	Body whorl width (mm)
<i>Aporrhais</i>	<i>Aporrhais pespelecani</i>	1	1	6	200	309	1.34	238	246	-0.01	14	-1.24	14
<i>Aporrhais</i>	<i>Aporrhais serresiana</i>	1	1	90	1000	275	1.36	102	133	-0.11	12	-1.04	12
<i>Rimellopsis</i>	<i>Rimellopsis laurenti</i>	1	0	59	280	1122	1.97	455	572	-0.1	55	-1.02	12

<i>Rostellariella</i>	<i>Rostellariella delicatula</i>	1	0	100	1100	2048	1.93	1230	1275	-0.02	46	-1.44	24
<i>Tibia</i>	<i>Tibia insulaechorab</i>	0	0	1	10	1492	1.54	699	808	-0.06	53	-1.18	43
<i>Varicospira</i>	<i>Varicospira cancellata</i>	1	0	3	60	542	1.89	242	288	-0.08	40	-0.86	7
<i>Terebellum</i>	<i>Terebellum delicatum</i>	1	0	5	31	565	1.85	230	251	-0.04	35	-0.86	8
<i>Terebellum</i>	<i>Terebellum terebellum</i> <i>C</i>	1	0	1	31	669	1.83	248	265	-0.03	33	-0.9	10
<i>Canarium</i> group	<i>Fusistrombus fusiformis</i>	0	0	2	62	1427	2.11	600	666	-0.05	89	-0.93	11
<i>Canarium</i> group I	" <i>Canarium</i> " <i>wilsonorum A</i>	1	0	2	105	784	1.99	360	372	-0.01	54	-0.84	8
<i>Canarium</i> group II	<i>Maculastrombus</i> <i>microureus</i>	1	0	1	22	724	2.01	322	339	-0.02	59	-0.76	7
<i>Canarium</i> group II	<i>Maculastrombus</i> <i>mutabilis B</i>	1	0	0	22	875	1.83	437	447	-0.01	62	-0.86	13
<i>Canarium</i> group III	<i>Canarium darwinense</i>	0	0	1	5	988	1.79	455	497	-0.04	64	-0.89	16
<i>Canarium</i> group III	<i>Canarium erythrinum</i>	1	0	8	46	1036	2.06	407	414	-0.01	68	-0.78	9
<i>Canarium</i> group III	<i>Canarium incisum</i>	1	0	0	40	1079	1.89	477	523	-0.04	59	-0.95	14
<i>Canarium</i> group III	<i>Canarium labiatum</i>	1	0	1	30	888	1.95	405	455	-0.05	65	-0.85	10
<i>Canarium</i> group III	<i>Canarium olydium</i>	0	0	1	25	845	1.72	361	420	-0.07	51	-0.92	16
<i>Conomurex</i>	<i>Conomurex decorus</i>	1	0	1	33	1465	1.69	661	670	-0.01	67	-1	30
<i>Conomurex</i>	<i>Conomurex fasciatus</i>	0	0	1	10	1240	1.98	560	591	-0.02	70	-0.93	13
<i>Conomurex</i>	<i>Conomurex luhuanus</i>	1	0	0	59	1618	1.87	667	690	-0.01	70	-0.99	22

<i>Conomurex</i>	<i>Conomurex persicus</i>	0	0	1	18	1320	1.82	709	822	-0.06	70	-1.07	20
<i>Euprotomus</i>	<i>Euprotomus aurisdiana</i>	0	0	1	100	1723	1.87	810	889	-0.04	85	-1.02	23
<i>Euprotomus</i>	<i>Euprotomus bulla</i>	1	0	0	46	1455	1.73	796	825	-0.02	67	-1.09	27
<i>Gibberulus</i>	<i>Gibberulus gibberulus</i>	1	0	1	33	1372	1.72	720	717	0	60	-1.08	26
<i>Gibberulus</i>	<i>Gibberulus gibbosus</i>	1	0	1	150	1311	1.82	567	627	-0.04	50	-1.1	20
<i>Harpago</i>	<i>Harpago chiragra</i>	0	0	6	22	2027	1.61	721	897	-0.09	49	-1.26	50
<i>Labiostrombus</i>	<i>Labiostrombus labiosus</i>	1	0	5	780	1132	1.85	420	456	-0.04	66	-0.84	16
<i>Labiostrombus</i>	<i>Labiostrombus pulchellus</i>	1	0	12	200	1040	1.94	570	603	-0.02	95	-0.8	12
<i>Labiostrombus</i>	<i>Labiostrombus wienekei</i>	0	0	5	37	811	1.87	448	428	0.02	61	-0.85	11
<i>Labiostrombus</i>	<i>Labiostrombus vittatus</i>	0	0	0	120	1794	1.93	780	890	-0.06	65	-1.14	21
<i>Labiostrombus</i>	<i>Labiostrombus turturella B</i>	1	0	0	15	1733	1.82	775	797	-0.01	69	-1.06	26
<i>Labiostrombus</i>	<i>Labiostrombus variabilis</i>	1	0	0	80	1511	2.03	650	607	0.03	67	-0.96	14
<i>Labiostrombus</i>	<i>Labiostrombus robustus</i>	1	0	0	55	1037	1.81	525	576	-0.04	59	-0.99	16
<i>Lambis</i>	<i>Lambis lambis A</i>	0	0	1	19	1691	1.72	530	636	-0.08	50	-1.1	32
<i>Lambis</i>	<i>Lambis lambis B</i>	0	0	0	19	1528	1.62	787	880	-0.05	51	-1.24	37
<i>Lambis</i>	<i>Lambis robusta</i>	0	0	10	30	1533	1.82	630	671	-0.03	62	-1.03	23
<i>Lambis</i>	<i>Lambis scorpius</i>	1	0	0	60	1571	1.92	735	821	-0.05	48	-1.23	19

<i>Lambis</i>	<i>Lambis truncata</i>	0	0	4	23	1579	1.24	800	1031	-0.11	62	-1.22	90
<i>Latissistrombus</i>	<i>Latissistrombus taurus</i>	1	0	1	50	1333	1.65	575	582	0	52	-1.05	30
<i>Lentigo</i>	<i>Lentigo lentiginosus</i>	1	0	1	35	2004	1.77	876	904	-0.01	79	-1.06	34
<i>Lentigo</i>	<i>Lentigo pipus</i>	1	0	5	100	1452	1.8	830	932	-0.05	65	-1.16	23
<i>Lentigo</i>	<i>Lentigo thersites</i>	0	0	2	40	2301	1.62	982	1112	-0.05	54	-1.31	55
<i>Lobatus</i>	<i>Lobatus raninus</i>	1	0	1	83	1311	1.64	660	704	-0.03	55	-1.11	30
<i>Ministrombus</i>	<i>Ministrombus minimus</i>	1	0	2	22	926	2.06	490	484	0	60	-0.91	8
<i>Ophioglossolambis</i>	<i>Ophioglossolambis digitata</i>	0	0	2	20	1132	1.54	502	685	-0.13	53	-1.11	33
<i>Strombus</i>	<i>Strombus pugilis</i>	0	1	0	91	1707	1.62	622	699	-0.05	69	-1.01	41
<i>Terestrombus</i>	<i>Terestrombus terebellatus</i>	1	0	3	30	1612	2.09	780	776	0	60	-1.11	13
<i>Thetystrombus</i>	<i>Thetystrombus latus</i>	1	1	1	37	1998	1.81	915	1030	-0.05	66	-1.19	31
<i>Tricornis</i>	<i>Tricornis tricornis</i>	0	0	1	20	1860	1.69	735	832	-0.05	48	-1.24	38
<i>Tridentarius</i>	<i>Tridentarius dentatus</i>	1	0	2	73	1724	2.06	576	608	-0.02	74	-0.91	15
<i>Pellicaria</i>	<i>Pellicaria vermis</i>	1	1	0	1150	360	0.93	220	232	-0.02	28	-0.92	42
<i>Struthiolaria</i>	<i>Struthiolaria papulosa</i>	0	1	0	141	350	1.2	240	247	-0.01	21	-1.07	22
Xenophoridae	<i>Onustus caribaeus</i>	1	1	9	1500	386	0.96	250	266	-0.03	22	-1.08	42
Xenophoridae	<i>Xenophora conchyliophora</i>	1	1	0	635	631	1.27	283	299	-0.02	25	-1.08	34
Xenophoridae	<i>Xenophora pallidula</i>	1	0	146	433	383	0.89	230	239	-0.02	24	-1	49

Xenophoridae	<i>Xenophora solariooides</i>	1	0	1	400	207	1.41	93	103	-0.04	15	-0.84	8
--------------	-------------------------------	---	---	---	-----	-----	------	----	-----	-------	----	-------	---

References

- Abbott D.P. 1962. Observations on the Gastropod *Terebellum terebellum* (Linnaeus) with particular reference to the behavior of the eyes during burrowing. *Veliger* 5:1-3.
- Abbott R.T. 1960. The genus *Strombus* in the Indo-Pacific. *Indo-Pac. Mollusca* 1:33-146.
- Abbott R.T. 1961. The genus *Lambis* in the Indo-Pacific. *Indo-Pac. Mollusca* 1:147-174.
- Abbott R.T. 1974. *American Seashells; The Marine Molluska of the Atlantic and Pacific Coasts of North America*. Van Nostrand Reinhold.
- Anand T.P., Samuel V.D., Edward J.P. 2001. Gastropod shells attached to the surface of *Xenophora pallidula* (Gastropoda, Prosobranchia). *Spec. Publ. Phuket Mar. Biol. Cent.* 25:363-365.
- Daccarett E.Y., Bossio V.M.S. 2011. *Colombian seashells from the Caribbean Sea*. L'informatore Piceno.
- Hayward B.W., Grace R.V., Brook F.J. 1981. Soft-bottom benthic macrofaunal communities of the eastern Bay of Islands, northern New Zealand. *Tane* 27:103-122.
- Hayward B.W., Morley M., Stephenson A.B., Blom W., Grenfell H., Prasad R. 1999. Marine biota of the north Taranaki coast, New Zealand. *Tane* 37:171-199.
- Janssen R., Zuschin M., Baal C. 2011. Gastropods and their habitats from the northern Red Sea (Egypt: Safaga): Part 2: Caenogastropoda: Sorbeoconcha and Littorinimorpha. *Ann. Naturhist. Mus. Wien, A*:373-509.
- Jarrett A.G. 2011. *Marine Shells of the Whitsunday Coast & Islands*. Alan G. Jarrett.

Kaullysing D., Taleb-Hossenkhan N., Kulkarni B.G., Bhagooli R. 2017. A comparison of the density and diversity of intertidal benthic molluscs at a sheltered and an exposed tropical coast around Mauritius Island. *West. Indian Ocean J. Mar. Sci.*:31-41.

Keen A.M. 1971. *Sea shells of tropical West America*. Stanford, California: Stanford University Press.

Kemp S., Sewell R.B.S. 1912. Notes on Decapoda in the Indian Museum. III. The species obtained by R.I.M.S.S. "Investigator" during the survey season 1910–1911. *Records of the Indian Museum* 7:15–32.

Kohn A.J. 1978. The Conidae (Mollusca: Gastropoda) of India. *J. Nat. Hist.* 12:295-335.

Kreipl K., Poppe G.T. 1999. The family Strombidae. In: Poppe GT, Groh K editors. *A Conchological Iconography*. Hackenheim, Germany, ConchBooks, p. 1-58.

Kronenberg G.C., Dharma B. 2005. New distributional records for four species of Stromboidea (Mollusca: Gastropoda) from Australasia. *Beagle: Records of the Museums and Art Galleries of the Northern Territory*, 21:47-51.

Kuroda T., Habe T., Oyama K. 1971. *The Sea Shells of Sagami Bay*. Tokyo: Maruzen.

Liverani V. 2013. The superfamily Stromboidea: addenda et corrigenda. In: Poppe GT, Groh K, Renker C editors. *A Conchological Iconography*, Harxheim, Germany, ConchBooks, p. 1-54.

Neef G. 1970. Notes on the subgenus Pelicaria. *N. Z. J. Geol. Geophys.* 13:436-476.

Ponder W.F. 1983. A revision of the Recent Xenophoridae of the world and of the Australian fossil species (Mollusca: Gastropoda). *Aust. Mus. Mem.* 17:1–126.

Severns M. 2001. *Hawaiian seashells*. Island Heritage Pub.

Tunnell J.W. 2010. *Encyclopedia of Texas seashells: identification, ecology, distribution, and history*. Texas A&M University Press.

Wells A. 1998. Superfamily Stromboidea. In: Beesley PL, Ross GJB, Wells A editors. *Mollusca: The Southern Synthesis* Melbourne, CSIRO, p. 766-774.

Wilson B.R., Wilson C., Baker P. 1993. *Australian Marine Shells: Prosobranch Gastropods, part one*. Australia: Odyssey.

Yonge C.M. 1937. The biology of *Aporrhais pes-pelecani* (L.) and *A. serresiana* (Mich.). *J. Mar. Biol. Assoc. U.K.* 21:687-703.